

Report 150705

Overview	Name	[overload 150705] php-fpm
	Description	php-fpm
	Status	FINISHED
	Identity	ff6h2nazzlxuljngtysl
	Creation date	2025-02-11 16:53:42.430+00:00
	Start date	2019-01-04 15:15:17.463+00:00
	End date	2019-01-04 15:25:22.247+00:00
	Target	185.147.80.168:None
	Configuration	ff6z5xdlfa5ehydedon7

Case: overall

Density distribution of response times

Response time quantiles

Network response codes

HTTP response codes

Instances

instances

RPS

Monitoring

Host ab61b3d4e7e718c27957cd5e6978f324

Memory

used

free

cached

buff

RPS

Net

System

cpu-cpu-total

diskio-vda1

diskio-vda2

net-eth0

netstat

Tables

Response time quantiles

Test	Case	q50	q75	q80	q85	q90	q95	q98	q99	q100
ff6h2nazzlxuljngtysl	overall	4.136	5.341	5.911	7.265	10.002	13.567	18.521	23.09	1030.772

Network response codes

Test	Case	0
ff6h2nazzlxuljngtysl	overall	285030

HTTP response codes

Test	Case	200
ff6h2nazzlxuljngtysl	overall	285030

Configurations

ff6z5xdlfa5ehydedon7

```

android:
  enabled: false
  package: yandextank.plugins.Android
autostop:
  autostop: []
  enabled: true
  package: yandextank.plugins.Autostop
  report_file: autostop_report.txt
bfg:
  enabled: false
  package: yandextank.plugins.Bfg
console:
  cases_max_spark: 120
  cases_sort_by: count
  disable_all_colors: false
  disable_colors: ''
  enabled: true
  info_panel_width: 33
  max_case_len: 32
  package: yandextank.plugins.Console
  short_only: false
  sizes_max_spark: 120
  times_max_spark: 120
core:
  affinity: ''
  artifacts_base_dir: ./logs
  artifacts_dir: null
  cmdline: /usr/local/bin/yandex-tank
  lock_dir: /var/lock/
  message: ''
  pid: 1
  taskset_path: taskset
  uuid: 485cdb57-bb70-4733-bd5d-69072614bdb8
influx:

```

```
enabled: false
package: yandextank.plugins.Influx
jmeter:
  enabled: false
  package: JMeter
json_report:
  enabled: true
  monitoring_log: monitoring.log
  package: yandextank.plugins.JsonReport
  test_data_log: test_data.log
overload:
  api_address: https://overload.yandex.net/
  api_attempts: 60
  api_timeout: 10
  chunk_size: 500000
  component: ''
  connection_timeout: 30
  enabled: true
  ignore_target_lock: false
  job_dsc: php-fpm
  job_name: php-fpm
  jobno_file: jobno_file.txt
  lock_targets: auto
  log_data_requests: false
  log_monitoring_requests: false
  log_other_requests: false
  log_status_requests: false
  maintenance_attempts: 10
  maintenance_timeout: 60
  meta:
    ammo_path: '/var/loadtest/ '
    cmdline: /usr/local/bin/yandex-tank
    jobno: 150705
    loop_count: 285029
    target_host: 185.147.80.168
    target_port: 8000
  network_attempts: 60
  network_timeout: 10
  notify: []
  operator: null
  package: yandextank.plugins.DataUploader
  send_status_period: 10
  strict_lock: false
  target_lock_duration: 30m
  task: ''
  threads_timeout: 60
  token_file: overload_token.txt
  ver: ''
  writer_endpoint: ''
phantom:
  additional_libs: []
  address: 185.147.80.168:8000
  affinity: ''
  ammo_limit: -1
  ammo_type: phantom
  ammofile: ''
  autocasess: 0
  buffered_seconds: 2
  cache_dir: null
  chosen_cases: ''
  client_certificate: ''
  client_cipher_suites: ''
  client_key: ''
  config: ''
  connection_test: true
  enabled: true
```

```
enum_ammo: false
file_cache: 8192
force_stepping: 0
gatling_ip: ''
header_http: '1.0'
headers: []
instances: 1000
load_profile:
  load_type: rps
  schedule: line(1, 500, 60s) const(500, 540s)
loop: -1
method_options: ''
method_prefix: method_stream
multi: []
package: yandextank.plugins.Phantom
phantom_http_entity: 8M
phantom_http_field: 8K
phantom_http_field_num: 128
phantom_http_line: 1K
phantom_modules_path: /usr/lib/phantom
phantom_path: phantom
phout_file: ''
port: ''
source_log_prefix: ''
ssl: false
tank_type: http
threads: null
timeout: 11s
uris:
- /
use_caching: true
writelog: all
rcassert:
  enabled: true
  fail_code: 10
  package: yandextank.plugins.RCAssert
  pass: ''
rcheck:
  disk_limit: 2048
  enabled: true
  interval: 10s
  mem_limit: 512
  package: yandextank.plugins.ResourceCheck
shellexec:
  catch_out: false
  enabled: true
  end: ''
  package: yandextank.plugins.ShellExec
  poll: ''
  post_process: ''
  prepare: ''
  start: ''
telegraf:
  config: monitoring.xml
  config_contents: "<Monitoring>\n <Host address=\"185.147.80.168\" interval=\"1\" \
  \ username=\"ansible\">\n <CPU/> <Kernel/> <Net/> <System/> <Memory/> <Disk/>\
  \ <Netstat /> <Nstat/>\n </Host>\n</Monitoring>\n"
  default_target: localhost
  disguise_hostnames: true
  enabled: true
  kill_old: false
  package: yandextank.plugins.Telegraf
  ssh_timeout: 30s
```